

A Master of Science project submitted to the
Graduate Program at the Institute of Physics, University of São Paulo

Title: Study of the angular polarimetric response of aerosols and their microphysical characteristics

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Abstract

Aerosols influence Earth's climate by directly altering solar and terrestrial radiation and indirectly modifying cloud properties. Their optical and physical properties exhibit much greater spatial and temporal variations than those of gaseous compounds. This project aims to quantify the angular responses of the polarized solar radiation signal reflected by aerosol populations and correlate them with independent estimates of microphysical aerosol quantities at two oceanic and two land sites in South America and Africa. To achieve this, we will integrate ground-based sunphotometer measurements with spaceborne polarimeter data. These datasets will provide a characterization of aerosol optical and physical properties, including size distribution, refractive index, and scattering phase function. We will then compare cases with contrasting dominance of the land-surface reflectance relative to the aerosol-layer signal to study the influence of surface radiative properties on the polarimetric angular fingerprint of aerosols. The results to be obtained in this project will help build a better understanding of aerosol microphysics and their spatial and temporal variations.

1. Introduction

Atmospheric aerosols are composed of microscopic particles that can affect the climate by interacting directly with solar and terrestrial radiation, as well as indirectly through changes in the optical properties of clouds (Haywood, 2021). Aerosols and their interactions with clouds are among the least understood contributors to climate change, and understanding their role is crucial for gaining a better understanding of the climate (IPCC, 2023). The quantity, particle size, shape, and chemical composition of aerosols are essential factors in determining their radiative impact on existing ecosystems and urban settings, which depends on the properties of aerosol sources present at each location (Yu and Zhang, 2011).

In the Amazon Basin, the natural biome contributes to both primary aerosol sources, i.e., particles directly emitted by vegetation, and secondary sources, in which volatile organic compounds emitted by vegetation are subsequently oxidized in the atmosphere to form aerosol particles (Martin et al., 2010). Other natural sources in the Amazon include sea salt near coastal areas, local and long-range-transported Saharan dust (Koren et al., 2006; Martin et al., 2010; Swap et al., 1992). Between August and October each year, however, anthropogenic biomass burning smoke is the most prevalent source of aerosols in the region, especially in the southern Amazon Basin (Ten Hoeve et al., 2012). Amazonian smoke aerosol particles are also transported downwind and spread across large fractions of the South American continent (Martins et al., 2018) and over the ocean. These particles induce micro- and macrophysical changes in cloud properties (Correia et al., 2021) and may change precipitation patterns.

Another significant anthropogenic aerosol source in South America is the pollution originating from vehicular combustion, particularly in large urban areas such as the Metropolitan Area of São Paulo (MASP). Vehicle displacement contributes to both primary and secondary aerosols and is also associated with the resuspension of soil dust (Pereira et al., 2024). In particular, the gas and particulate phases of pollution in the megacity of São Paulo are influenced

by both vehicular combustion of fossil fuels, primarily diesel and gasoline, and the use of renewable fuels, such as ethanol (Brito et al., 2015). Adding to this complex scenario, the MASP can also be affected by long-range-transported biomass-burning aerosols (Pereira et al., 2021; Yamasoe et al., 2017).

Figure 1. Phase function (p_1 , left panels) and the signed degree of linear polarization ($-p_5/p_1$, right panels) for biomass burning aerosols and dust aerosols, calculated using Mie theory. Extracted from Hasekamp and Landgraf (2007).

Because the optical, physical, and chemical properties of aerosol particles exhibit strong spatial and temporal variability, the use of satellite-based remote sensing techniques is inescapable for better understanding the role of aerosols in climate. This technique has been used for decades, relying on multispectral radiometric measurements of reflected solar radiation with prescribed, fixed aerosol and surface radiative properties to derive aerosol information. However, Mishchenko and Travis (1997) have shown that single-view intensity-only satellite imagery cannot fully overcome the uniqueness problem when estimating the full spatial-temporal heterogeneity of aerosol properties. These authors have also shown that multi-angle polarimetric measurements are sufficient to solve the uniqueness problem if surface reflectance properties are known a priori. As an example, Fig. 1 shows the scattering phase function and the signed degree of linear

polarization, for biomass burning and dust aerosols, calculated from rigorous Mie theory (Hasekamp and Landgraf, 2007). By combining measurements at multiple wavelengths with observations at multiple scattering angles, the analysis of the scattered radiation phase function (Fig. 1, left panels) and the signed degree of linear polarization (Fig. 1, right panels) provides sufficient information to distinguish different aerosol sources.

In general, temporal and spatial variations in surface properties, especially over land, pose difficulties in assuming such properties are known. The use of climatological (i.e., long-term averages) surface properties is appropriate over the ocean, but often leads to large uncertainties over land (Waquet et al., 2010, 2009). Hasekamp and Landgraf (2007) have shown that only multi-viewing measurements of intensity and polarization can provide sufficient information content to simultaneously retrieve aerosol and surface properties with the necessary accuracy for climate research. Fig. 2 shows the simulated error in retrieving the aerosol optical depth as a function of solar illumination for biomass burning and dust aerosols, assuming unknown surface reflectance properties (Hasekamp and Landgraf, 2007). For a simulated optical depth of 0.3, the retrieval error can vary between about 0.1 and 0.2, depending on the type of aerosol and solar illumination, if only the radiation intensity is considered. When the intensity and the linear polarimetric signal were taken into account, the error was about 0.02, independent of aerosol type and solar illumination.

Figure 2. Simulations of the 550 nm aerosol optical depth retrieval error ($\Delta\tau_{550}$), as a function of the solar zenith angle (SZA), for measurement types including radiation intensity only (I), or intensity and linear polarization (I,q,u), for biomass burning and dust aerosols. The surface properties were treated as unknown parameters, and $\tau_{550} = 0.3$ was used in all simulations. Extracted from Hasekamp and Landgraf (2007).

We propose studying the angular dependence of the reflected polarimetric signal from various aerosol-surface types, measured by a satellite sensor over both land and ocean, and comparing these signatures with aerosol properties retrieved from surface sunphotometers. The Aerosol Robotic Network (AERONET) is a worldwide network maintained by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), composed of solar photometers that perform

collimated measurements of direct and diffuse descending solar radiation at the surface, at various wavelengths (Giles et al., 2019; Holben et al., 2006, 1998). There are several AERONET sites worldwide, including in the southern Amazon Basin (e.g., Alta Floresta, MT) and in São Paulo, where one can sample natural biogenic, biomass burning, and urban aerosols, and others at islands off the west coast of South America (e.g., San Cristobal, Galapagos Isl.) and Africa (e.g., Cape Verde), that can retrieve properties of sea salt aerosols, transported biomass burning, or Saharan dust aerosols. The island sites provide optimal oceanic background surface properties for satellite sensor measurements, while land sites can be more challenging. The photometers measure the attenuation of direct solar radiation at several wavelengths, allowing the calculation of the aerosol optical depth (AOD) and other quantities. Diffuse radiation measurements allow inference of other average (columnar) physical properties of the atmospheric aerosol, such as its size distribution, complex refractive index, and phase function, all of which can influence the polarized signal detected from space.

The Plankton, Aerosol, Cloud, ocean Ecosystem (PACE) satellite mission, managed by NASA (Werdell et al., 2019), has a hyperspectral imager, the Ocean Color Instrument (OCI), and two multi-angle polarimeters, the Spectro-polarimeter for Planetary Exploration (SPEXone) and the Hyper Angular Research Polarimeter (HARP2). The OCI aims to quantify the concentrations of different phytoplankton species, the distribution of chlorophyll, and the concentrations of organic carbon and particulate matter dissolved in water, among other products, over the oceans. Across the continents, the OCI measures the hyperspectral reflectance of the surface and infers parameters related to aerosols and clouds, including optical depth, thermodynamic phase, and effective radius of solid and liquid particles in clouds, among other parameters (Remer, Davis, et al., 2019). The polarimeters combine hyperspectral (SPEXone) and hyperangular (HARP2) measurements, thereby providing access to a wide range of information about the scattered radiation signal, which enables simultaneous inferences of aerosol and surface properties. In the coming years, this configuration design for the polarimeters is expected to allow at least a doubling of the number of degrees of freedom of information obtained from the aerosol layer compared to previous satellite missions. In this way, it will be possible to obtain highly accurate inferences about the physical properties of aerosols, such as size distribution, complex refractive index, or single scattering albedo (Remer, Knobelspiesse, et al., 2019).

In this project, we will characterize the HARP2 angular polarimetric response of aerosols and surface properties at two land and two ocean locations, and then compare these results with AERONET inversions and direct-sun measurements. These detailed analyses will shed light on the polarimetric signatures of aerosols, their angular and spectral dependence, and help mitigate uncertainties surrounding the coupling between surface and aerosol optical properties.

1.1 Scientific objectives

This plan aims to study aerosol microphysical and optical properties retrieved from surface and space-based remote sensing, in selected cases over the land and ocean, from 20024 to 2025.

This project has the following specific objectives:

- a) To characterize the combined aerosol-surface polarimetric angular response measured by HARP2 in representative cases dominated by biomass burning, dust, urban, biogenic, and sea salt aerosols;
- b) To characterize aerosol optical and microphysical properties retrieved by AERONET, colocated with HARP2 measurements, including the aerosol optical depth, single scattering albedo, asymmetry parameter, complex refractive index, size distribution, and phase function;
- c) To critically correlate HARP2 results with the corresponding AERONET retrievals, contrasting cases where the aerosol or the surface is the dominant signal source, over the land or ocean.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Stokes parameters and radiation scattering

The physical basis for polarimetric measurements stems from solving Maxwell's equations for a propagating electromagnetic wave in vacuum (Jackson, 2009), which one can arbitrarily set along the \hat{z} direction in Euclidean coordinates. In general, the electric field vector \vec{E} is described as (Trippe, 2014):

$$\vec{E} = \vec{E}_o \cos(\omega t - kz - \phi) \quad (1)$$

where \vec{E}_o is the electric field vector at the initial time and position, t is the time, ω is the angular frequency, $k = \omega/c$ is the wave vector modulus, c is the speed of light, and ϕ is an arbitrary phase. The electric field vector can be described in terms of its projections E_x and E_y along the \hat{x} and \hat{y} directions as:

$$\begin{aligned} E_x &= E_{ox} \cos(\omega t - kz - \phi_x) \\ E_y &= E_{oy} \cos(\omega t - kz - \phi_y) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where E_{ox} and E_{oy} are the projections along the \hat{x} and \hat{y} directions of the electric field vector at the initial time and position, and ϕ_x and ϕ_y are arbitrary phase angles. The polarization of the wave is determined by the relative values of E_{ox} , E_{oy} , ϕ_x , and ϕ_y (Trippe, 2014).

A satellite sensor measures radiation intensity rather than the magnitudes of electric fields. Taking the electric field vector from Eq. (1), the radiation intensity I is:

$$I = \langle \epsilon_o c \vec{E} \cdot \vec{E} \rangle = \epsilon_o c [\langle E_x^2 \rangle + \langle E_y^2 \rangle] \quad (3)$$

where $\langle \rangle$ denotes time average, and ϵ_o is the vacuum permittivity. For simplicity, we omit the constants $\epsilon_o c$ and write the Stokes parameters, four characteristic intensities that define the polarization state of the wave, as:

$$\begin{aligned} I &= \langle E_x^2 \rangle + \langle E_y^2 \rangle \\ Q &= \langle E_x^2 \rangle - \langle E_y^2 \rangle \\ U &= 2 \langle E_x E_y \cos(\phi_y - \phi_x) \rangle \\ V &= 2 \langle E_x E_y \sin(\phi_y - \phi_x) \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where I is the total intensity of the wave, Q and U describe the magnitude and orientation of the linear polarization, and V describes the helicity and magnitude of the circular polarization (Waquet et al., 2009). The set of four quantities shown in Eq. (4) constitutes the Stokes intensity vector \vec{S} , as:

$$\vec{S} = \begin{bmatrix} I \\ Q \\ U \\ V \end{bmatrix} = [I, Q, U, V]^T \quad (5)$$

In this notation, completely unpolarized light is represented as:

$$[I, 0, 0, 0]^T \quad (6)$$

while completely polarized light is represented by:

$$[\sqrt{Q^2 + U^2 + V^2}, Q, U, V]^T \quad (7)$$

The degree of polarization is given by:

$$p = \frac{\sqrt{Q^2 + U^2 + V^2}}{I} \quad (8)$$

and the degree of linear polarization¹ is given by (Hovenier et al., 2004):

$$p_l = \frac{\sqrt{Q^2 + U^2}}{I} \quad (9)$$

Radiation scattering processes, for instance, between an original intensity vector \vec{S}_o and a scattered vector \vec{S}_s , can be described as:

$$\vec{S}_s = M\vec{S}_o \quad (10)$$

where M is a 4x4 scattering matrix. The 16 elements of the M matrix are constructed from at most 7 independent real quantities (Hovenier et al., 2004). Therefore, these elements are interrelated by various equations, depending on the type of scattering problem. For this project, the relevant type of scattering matrix is given by:

$$P(\Theta) = \begin{bmatrix} p_1(\Theta) & p_5(\Theta) & 0 & 0 \\ p_5(\Theta) & p_2(\Theta) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & p_3(\Theta) & p_6(\Theta) \\ 0 & 0 & -p_6(\Theta) & p_4(\Theta) \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

where Θ is the scattering angle (i.e., the angle between the original radiation beam and the scattered one) and the elements $p_i(\Theta)$ are functions dependent only on the scattering angle, and specific for a given scatterer type, shape, and size parameter. This particular type of $P(\Theta)$ matrix is valid for scattering by an assembly of randomly oriented, symmetric particles, by an assembly containing particles and their mirror particles in equal numbers and with random orientations, and for Rayleigh scattering with or without depolarization effects (Hovenier et al., 2004). This condition matches a typical representation of sunlight being scattered by a population of aerosol particles, which is why this $P(\Theta)$ type is important to this project. The first element in the matrix, p_1 , is the phase function, the only element remaining if polarization is ignored in a scattering problem. The ratio, $-p_5/p_1$, is the signed degree of linear polarization. Both p_1 and $-p_5/p_1$ are shown in Fig. 1 for a simulation of scattered radiation from populations of biomass burning and dust aerosol particles. More broadly, we can say $P(\Theta)$ represents the angular response of the scattered polarized radiation, which is sensitive to the microphysical characteristics of the aerosol population.

2.2 AERONET retrievals

AERONET photometers perform two types of measurements: direct solar radiation and diffuse radiation. Direct radiation is measured by the photometer in cloudless conditions, when its collimator points directly at the sun. Three measurements (triplets) are performed, each taking approximately 10 seconds. The triplet sample standard deviation of these measurements is used to detect clouds. The measurement interval between triplets varies throughout the day, typically every 15 minutes or less if no rain is detected. Measurements identified as valid (i.e., cloudless) are used to derive the optical depth of aerosols at wavelengths of 340, 380, 440, 500, 675, 870, 1020, and 1640 nm, the amount of water vapor present in the vertical column, and the Angstrom exponent between wavelength pairs (Holben et al., 1998). For diffuse radiation measurements, the photometer collimator points at the sky away from the direct solar beam, at specific angles, and records the scattered radiation at constant zenith angle (Almucantar scan) or along the solar plane (principal plane scan). Sky radiance measurements are used in AERONET inversion codes to

¹ Notice that the "Lidar depolarization ratio" is a distinct quantity, given by $(I-Q)/(I+Q)$.

derive quantities such as scattering phase function, particle size distribution, asymmetry factor, single scattering albedo, and complex refractive index. Diffuse measurements occur less frequently than direct ones because they require more restrictive physical conditions, with the absence of clouds at a certain number of observation angles.

AERONET's internal algorithm processes all measurements as soon as they are made, classifying the data quality into levels 1.0, 1.5, and 2.0 (Holben et al., 2006). Level 1.0 is raw data from successful measurements. Level 1.5 is cloud-screened data, also distributed within a few minutes of acquisition. Level 2.0 data are obtained from periodic intercalibrations of each photometer, using a standard reference photometer maintained by NASA. This intercalibration process requires each photometer to be physically transported to a NASA campus, typically once a year. For this reason, Level 2.0 data can generally be delayed in becoming available, but is preferable for research use. In this project, we will use Level 2.0 data whenever possible and Level 1.5 data otherwise.

2.3 PACE/HARP2 measurements and retrievals

PACE has an ascending polar orbit with a nominal mean equator crossing time of 13:00 local time, and a repeat cycle of 2 days. HARP2 aboard the PACE satellite is a hyperangular imaging polarimeter that provides microphysical information on aerosol particles and clouds, as well as the properties of land and water surfaces. The lateral swath spans 1,550 km, with ground pixels measuring 1.3 x 2.0 km. The sensor measures the polarized radiance at three angles of linear polarization, at 0°, 45°, and 90°, in 10 along-track viewing angles for spectral bands of 440, 550, and 870 nm, and 60 viewing angles for a 670 nm band (Martins et al., 2024). From these measurements, the processing algorithm derives the characteristic Stokes intensities I, Q, and U, i.e., the total scattered radiation and the linear polarization components. Although aerosols scatter circularly polarized light (Gassó and Knobelspiesse, 2022), the circular polarization is typically several orders of magnitude smaller than linear polarization (Waquet et al., 2009). Therefore, the V intensity is not measured by PACE polarimeters.

HARP2 polarization measurements are processed in data levels. Level 1a are the original raw data images, at the instrument spatial resolution; Level 1b corresponds to calibrated and geolocated data files, at the instrument spatial resolution; Level 1c are calibrated and geolocated data files, projected onto a common PACE grid, at 5 km spatial resolution. Level 2 data contain derived geophysical variables such as the AOD, complex refractive index, and many other quantities related to aerosols, clouds, and oceanic surface properties (Martins et al., 2024). Currently, all Level 1 data is available at NASA's Earthdata website. Level 2 cloud data is also available over land and ocean (McBride et al., 2020). Aerosol Level 2 data is available over the ocean, derived from inversions using the FastMAPOL algorithm (Gao et al., 2023, 2021). Over land, aerosol Level 2 data are still under development and will be made available by applying the Generalized Retrieval of Aerosol and Surface Properties (GRASP) algorithm (Chen et al., 2020; Dubovik et al., 2014). GRASP analyzes the measured polarized radiance data and simultaneously derives aerosol and surface reflectance properties, including aerosol size distribution, spectral refractive index, degree of sphericity, and others. This algorithm accommodates various sets of boundary conditions, including bright land surfaces, which have posed challenges for traditional retrieval algorithms. GRASP is free to download and use, but it is highly complex and computationally expensive software.

2.4 Data analysis

For this project, we will explore HARP2 Level 1c data to characterize the angular response of Stokes intensities and Level 2 aerosol data over the ocean, which can be compared to AERONET retrievals. We may investigate using GRASP over the land to invert Level 1c polarized radiances,

seeking to retrieve aerosol microphysical quantities. To achieve the project's goals, will begin by characterizing the physical and optical properties of atmospheric aerosols from AERONET and HARP2 at the two selected oceanic locations: Cape Verde and San Cristobal. The seasonal characterization of aerosols and the oceanic surface reflectance at these locations will provide core information on sea salt, biomass burning (San Cristobal), and Saharan dust (Cape Verde) aerosols. Next, we will characterize the seasonal signal at the two land sites selected in the project: the MASP and Alta Floresta in the southern Amazon Basin, for which AERONET inversions and HARP2 Level 1c data are available. This will yield results on the angular dependence of polarimetric radiances for natural biogenic, biomass burning (Alta Floresta), and urban (MASP) aerosols.

AERONET sunphotometers have been running for years or decades at the four locations chosen for this project. It represents a robust aerosol dataset, but with limited spatial representativeness over large continental areas compared to what satellite sensors can achieve. On the other hand, HARP2 has a relatively short history, having been launched in 2024; however, it can assess atmospheric conditions over much broader areas compared to stationary surface sensors. Therefore, one key step for this project will be comparing AERONET and HARP2 retrievals over the ocean during matchup overpass opportunities. These comparisons will allow us to determine the extent to which satellite sensor retrievals can be used to characterize the spatial variability of aerosol micro- and macrophysical parameters, as well as surface reflectance properties. In comparing AERONET and HARP2, we note that HARP2's lack of wavelengths above 870 nm indicates its performance might be degraded if seeking to reproduce AERONET's microphysical retrievals for coarse aerosol particles with diameters above 2 μm (Remer et al., 2019). In the context of this project, such a characteristic can be relevant for the characterization of Saharan dust aerosols.

Surface properties are also a key parameter to be considered in the project. Over land, the surface reflectance signal is likely to dominate the upwelling shortwave radiance measured by HARP2 under low AOD conditions (e.g., when studying natural biogenic or urban aerosols). On the other hand, during the biomass burning season in the southern Amazon Basin, there are frequent events of very high AOD levels, for which the surface signal can be negligible compared to the scattered radiation from the aerosol plume. We will investigate how the surface-aerosol coupling can be translated into an angular polarimetric signature under such contrasting conditions.

3. Expected results and challenges to be addressed

The project's technical feasibility is discussed next. Access to the relevant datasets for this project is freely available on the internet via several web portals, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Data or code sources and accession addresses.

Source	Accession address
AERONET	https://aeronet.gsfc.nasa.gov/
PACE/HARP2	https://search.earthdata.nasa.gov/
GRASP	https://www.grasp-open.com/

This project will be restricted to the years 2024 and 2025. For this timespan, all the relevant data needed for the project has already been processed and is available on the websites listed in Table 1. As mentioned previously, Level 2 aerosol data for HARP2 over land are still in development. A priori, this dataset will not be used in the project. However, if feasible, we will use GRASP with Level 1c data to derive aerosol properties over land in representative cases.

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